

The Relationship Between The Power Supply System and The Physical Medium, The Connection Between Different Parts of a Nanosystem, and The Dimensions of Nanoantennas

Mohammad Naser-Moghadasi , Professor

Faculty member Islamic Azad University of Science and Research Branch, Tehran

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0282-2916>

Dr.Afshin Rashid , Assistant Professor

Faculty member Islamic Azad University of Science and Research Branch, Tehran

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2343-1631>

- **Abstract:**

- Note : The dimensions of the antenna and the nanosystem or nanosensor assembly, operating frequency, power losses, range and dimensions of the sensor network, structure and capabilities of the power supply system, and the physical communication platform between the different parts of a nanosystem are major factors and parameters, each of which is decisive in some way and determines the manufacturing capability and performance of the final system.

- **Keywords:** Nanocommunications , terahertz , electromagnetic waves , nanoantenna

Introduction •

Nano-network is a nano- scale communication network between nano-devices. Nano-devices face special challenges in performance due to their limited processing and power management capabilities . Therefore, these devices are expected to perform simple tasks that require different and novel approaches. In a molecular communication system, the transmitter sends information using chemical molecules called information molecules, which are then received and decoded by a communication receiver after being released into the environment. A network of communication nanoparticles can cover a wider area and perform more network processing . In addition, there are several nano-communication technologies that require the use of external excitation and measurement to work. Wireless communication between nano-networks and micro- and macro-devices and equipment can meet this need. In general, in order to receive an electromagnetic wave in space, the dimensions of the antenna must be on the order of the wavelength of the incoming wave to its surface. Due to the very small dimensions of nanosensors, nanoantennas need to operate at very high frequencies to be usable. The use of graphene helps to solve this problem to a great extent. The propagation speed of waves in CNTs and GNRs can be up to 100 times lower than in vacuum, and this depends on the physical structure, temperature and energy. Accordingly, the resonant frequency of graphene-based nanoantennas can be two orders of magnitude lower than that of nanoantennas based on carbon nanomaterials. It has been mathematically and theoretically proven that a quasi-metallic carbon nanotube can emit terahertz radiation when a time-varying voltage is applied to its sides. Despite the possibilities of manufacturing nanotubes with a length of several centimeters, it is possible to manufacture electrical conductors with a length-to-width ratio of the order of 10^7 . Nanotube antennas at first glance give us the impression that they are similar to a dipole antenna designed in small dimensions. But in fact, this is not the case. In the main theory of dipole antennas to determine the current distribution on the antenna, the dipole radius is larger than the skin depth and the resistance losses are so small that they can be ignored.

The most important parameters of each nano antenna (from electromagnetic current distribution to examining important properties of nano antennas)

One of the most important parameters of any nanoantenna is the current distribution on it. This characteristic determines the radiation pattern, radiation resistance and reactance, and many important properties of the nanoantenna. Despite the possibilities of making nanotubes with a length of several centimeters, it is possible to make electrical conductors with a length-to-width ratio of the order of 10^7 . At first glance, nanotube antennas give the impression that they are similar to dipole antennas designed in small dimensions. But in fact, this is not the case. In the main theory of dipole antennas, to determine the current distribution on the antenna, the dipole radius is larger than the skin depth and the resistance losses are so small that they can be ignored. Since the nanodipole L/d is significantly reduced, it becomes unusable. In one-dimensional electrical conductors such as nanotubes, the skin depth mode is completely eliminated. This is because here the electrons are only allowed to move along the conductor strand and therefore the current distribution is effectively one-dimensional. In addition to the fact that the electrons move in only one dimension, two other important issues also occur, inductance and large resistance. These features create a very different behavior for nanotube antennas compared to classical antennas. The main difference in the Nano Antenna is that the current distribution is alternating with a wavelength that is 100 times smaller than the free space

wavelength for a given thermal frequency. The wavelength of the current distribution depends on the wave speed in that mode. If the wave speed is the speed of light, the wavelength of the current distribution is the wavelength of electromagnetic waves in free space. On the other hand, the wave speed in nanotubes is about 100 times slower than the speed of light. This is because in circuit theory, the wave speed is equal to the inverse square root of the capacitive capacitance per unit length multiplied by the inductive capacitance per unit length. The kinetic inductance per unit length of a nanotube is ten thousand times greater than the magnetic inductance per unit length of conventional antennas. Therefore, the wave speed will be 100 times smaller than the speed of light. The efficiency of a classic nanotube antenna is of the order of -90 dB, which will be due to resistive losses. This is while the dimensions of the antenna and the nanosystem or nanosensor assembly, operating frequency, power losses, range and dimensions of the sensor network, the structure and facilities of the power supply system and the physical communication platform between the different parts of a nanosystem are major factors and parameters, each of which is in some way decisive and determines the manufacturing capability and performance of the final system.

Nano-antenna as the primary means of absorbing nano-electromagnetic waves in nano-telecommunication

Nano antennas are considered as the primary means of absorbing electromagnetic nanowaves in space and nanocommunications, and have their own related engineering knowledge, which is very developed and extensive. In general, in order to receive an electromagnetic wave in space, the dimensions of the antenna must be on the order of the wavelength entering its surface. Given the very small dimensions of nanosensors, nanoantennas need to have a very high operating frequency in order to be usable. The use of graphene helps to solve this problem to a large extent. The propagation speed of waves in CNTs and GNRs can be up to 100 times lower than its speed in vacuum, and this is due to the physical structure, temperature and energy. Accordingly, the resonant frequency of graphene-based nanoantennas can be two orders of magnitude lower than that of nanoantennas based on nanocarbon materials. It has been proven mathematically and theoretically that a quasi-metallic carbon nanotube can have terahertz radiation when a time-varying voltage is applied to its sides. One of the most important parameters of any nanoantenna is the current distribution on it. This characteristic determines the radiation pattern, radiation resistance and reactance, and many important properties of the antenna. Despite the possibilities of manufacturing nanotubes with a length of several centimeters, it is possible to manufacture electrical conductors with a length to width ratio of the order of 10^7 . Nanotube antennas at first glance give us the impression that they are similar to a dipole antenna designed in small dimensions. But in fact, this is not the case. In the main theory of dipole antennas to determine the current distribution on the antenna, the dipole radius is larger than the skin depth and the resistance losses are so small that they can be ignored. Given that the nanodipole L/d is significantly reduced, it becomes unusable. In one-dimensional electrical conductors such as nanotubes, the skin depth mode is completely eliminated. Because here the electrons are only allowed to move along the length of the conductor, and so the current distribution is effectively one-dimensional. In addition to the fact that the electrons move in only one dimension, two other important issues arise: large inductance and resistance. These features give nanotube antennas a very different behavior than classical antennas. The main difference is that the current distribution is alternating with a wavelength that is 100 times smaller than the free-space wavelength for a given thermal frequency. The wavelength of the current distribution depends on

the wave speed in that mode. If the wave speed is the speed of light, the wavelength of the current distribution is the wavelength of electromagnetic waves in free space. On the other hand, the wave speed in nanotubes is about a hundred times slower than the speed of light. This is because in circuit theory, the wave speed is equal to the inverse square root of the capacitive capacitance per unit length multiplied by the inductive capacitance per unit length.

(Nanoelectronics Plasmonic) Model experiments with, for example, microwaves and larger metal structures

Since the material parameters vary significantly with frequency. In particular, this means that model experiments with, for example, microwaves and larger metal structures cannot replace experiments with metal nanostructures at optical frequencies. Surface charge density fluctuations associated with surface nanoplasmons at the interface between a metal and a dielectric can give rise to strongly enhanced optical near-fields that are spatially confined near the metal surface. Similarly, if the electron gas is confined in three dimensions, such as a small particle, the overall displacement of the electrons relative to the positively charged lattice leads to a restoring force that in turn gives rise to specific particle-plasmons. Resonance depends on the geometry of the particle. In suitably shaped particles (usually sharp-pointed), local charge accumulations associated with strongly enhanced optical fields can occur. Changes in some properties, such as conductivity in nanotransistors and electromagnetic properties in nanowires, can occur on a scale of just a few nanometers. The enhancement of surface plasmons in nanometer-sized structures is called localized surface plasmon enhancement. Patterning magnetic materials into arrays of nanoscale dots can lead to a very strong and highly controllable change in the polarization of light when the beam is reflected from the array. This discovery could increase the sensitivity of optical components for telecommunications and biosensing applications. Coupling between light and magnetism in electrical nanostructures Localized Surface Plasmons arise from quantum nanoelectronic interactions. These interactions lead to magneto-optical effects that change properties, such as the polarization axis or the intensity of light. Interactions between light and matter increase at the nanoscale. This is a key motivation in the field of plasmonics, which uses the interaction of light with metallic nanostructures to create nanoelectronic devices. In the structure of localized surface plasmons, a nano-sized metal nanoparticle acts much like an antenna for visible wavelengths. Such antennas for us in many everyday devices that operate at much longer radio and microwave wavelengths take advantage of a phenomenon called surface lattice resonance, in which all the nanoparticles, tiny antennas, radiate in unison in an array. The key to this is assembling magnetic nanoantennas on a length scale that matches the wavelength of the incoming light. In periodic arrays, the nanoparticles interact strongly with each other, causing collective oscillations. Such behavior has been previously observed in metallic nanoparticles.

(Plasmonic waves) Electromagnetic waves and conduction electrons

These nanostructures consist of metal and dielectric, whose dimensions are below the excitation wavelength (the wavelength of the radiation that excites the plasmonic waves). Further compression of the structure of electronic devices and appliances with the help of plasmonics science has led to the study and use of plasmonic structures and plasmonic waves. Plasmonics is based on the interaction process between electromagnetic waves and conduction electrons in metals with nano-sized dimensions. Analytically, the reason for the rapid energy loss of

electrons passing through metals is that this energy is spent on the cumulative and oscillatory motion of free electrons in the metal, which he called plasmons. With the technological approach towards the accumulation of optoelectronic circuits, the manufacturing problems and phenomena that helped prevent further compression of the structure have led to the study and use of plasmonic structures and plasmonic waves. These nanostructures consist of metal and dielectric, whose dimensions are below the excitation wavelength (the wavelength of the radiation that excites the plasmonic waves). In electronic science, the topic of nano is centered around (nano memories; nanochips and fast nanochips and nanoelectronic components) with less weight and greater efficiency. Nanotechnology is the science, engineering and technology at the nanoscale or in other words, the study of the application of very small objects and their use in all fields of science such as chemistry, biology, electronics; materials science and engineering. The history of nanotechnology describes the development of concepts and experimental work carried out in the field of nanotechnology. Although nanotechnology is one of the recent advances in scientific research, the development of its fundamental concepts has occurred over a long period. Various types of nanotechnologies, such as further compaction of the structure of electronic devices and appliances, etc., cannot cope with all the practical demands of industrial applications in terms of high resolution, high power, low cost, large area and patterns on non-flat and curved surfaces. Therefore, new high-volume nano-manufacturing technology is in dire need of exploitation and development to meet the extraordinary needs of growing markets.

The tasks of the nano transmitter TN and receiver RN are operational such as (performing baseband processing , frequency conversion, filtering, and amplifying waves).

The TN nanotransmitter and RN electromagnetic receiver must be able to perform operations such as performing baseband processing , frequency conversion, filtering, and amplification of waves for the signals it sends or those that reach the nanoantenna from free space. Nano particles in the TN nanotransmitter and RN electromagnetic nanoreceiver must be able to perform operations such as performing baseband processing, frequency conversion, filtering, and amplification of nanowaves for the signals it sends or those that reach the nanoantenna from free space. Data transfer between nanosensors can lead to increased capabilities and applications of nanodevices compared to their standalone operation mode, in terms of both complexity and range of functionality.

Functions in nanotransmitter TN and nanoreceiver RN in nanocommunication

Molecular communication is a natural communication method used by living organisms (e.g., pheromone communication) and is predicted to become a portable method for future nanodevices. The concentration of a molecule in the close vicinity of the receiver may be used to sense the transmitter of the molecular bit being sent. Quantum communication is based on the transfer of entangled pairs from one location to another, using exchange, repetition, and purification. Quantum interference or quantum parallelism gives us enormous computational power, especially in source coding, where information about the entire content is needed instead of individual inputs. FRET is a non-radiative energy transfer process between fluorescent molecules based on dipole-dipole interactions of the molecules. Energy is rapidly transferred from a donor to an acceptor molecule in close proximity, such as 0 to 10 nm, without the emission of a photon. Low dependence on environmental factors, control of its parameters, and

relatively wide transmission range make FRET suitable for high-speed nanoscale communication channels.

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